

Figure. Mode of interaction of mono-phosphorylated PTEN C-tail with VSP. a, Overlay of ^{15}N - ^1H -HSQC spectra of VSP alone (blue) and VSP in the presence of 4 molar equivalent mono-phosphorylated PTEN C-tail at position Ser380 (red). Selected residues of the CBR III and C α 2 loops are showed with arrows. b, Combined chemical shift perturbations corresponding to spectra in (a) and plotted against VSP primary sequence. Dashed red line corresponds to the standard deviation to the mean, excluding outliers (higher than 3xSDM). Notable regions of VSP for their strong interaction or biological relevance are shown in colored areas. c, Structure of VSP (PDB:3V0G) colored according to NMR results. Unassigned residues are in grey. Assigned residues that do not experience significant chemical shift perturbations or peak intensity changes are shown in light blue for the C2 domain and light green for the catalytic domain. Residues that show significant perturbations are shown in red.